

PERISTALTIC FLOW OF A COUPLE STRESS FLUID THROUGH A TAPERED ASYMMETRIC CHANNEL APPLICATION TO EMBRYO TRANSPORT IN UTERINE CAVITY

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ABSTRACT

The peristaltic transport of a couple stress fluids in the asymmetric channel is examined, concealed by long wavelength and low Reynolds number assumptions. The tapered asymmetric channel is produced due to the peristaltic wave on the walls of the non-uniform channel having alternative phases and amplitudes. Excellent results for the axial velocity, pressure gradient and stream function have been determined. Numerical evaluation has also been found for investigating the pumping characteristics with various flow values of parameters. It has been shown that the peristaltic flow pumping decreases with an increase in non-uniform theological parameters. Further, our conclusion is created to be very relevant to Srivastava and Srivastava [23] when the absence of the tapered asymmetric nature of the channel and couple stress fluid parameter.

KEYWORDS

Peristaltic Transport; Couple-Stress Fluid; Tapered asymmetric channel

1. INTRODUCTION

Physiologists have found that peristaltic flow plays a key role in transport of fluid in many biological systems. Especially, a peristaltic mechanism may be regarded in chyme movement in the gastrointestinal tract, in transport of the ovum in female fallopian tube, in urine transport from kidney to bladder through urethra and also in industries for the transport of noxious fluid in nuclear industries, as well as in roller pumps, in blood pumps, in heart lung machine, vasomotion of small blood vessels, and many others. The problem of the mechanism of peristaltic flow has attracted the care of many detectives since the first investigation of Latham [1]. The initial

mathematical model of peristalsis viewed by train of sinusoidal waves in an infinitely long symmetric channel or tube has been initially studied by Shapiro et al. [2] and Fung and Yahi [3]. Later, researchers have extended a number of analytical, numerical and experimental studies of peristaltic flow of different fluids have been reported under different conditions with reference to physiological and mechanical situations (Refs. [4-8] and references therein).

Undoubtedly, the most of physiological and industrial fluids including blood act as non-Newtonian fluids. Since, the observer of peristaltic flow of non-Newtonian fluids may assist to get better realizing of the biological systems. Even the latest researchers in the field are expecting for the analysis of peristaltic flows under different aspects [9-14]. It is a well known fact that, couple stress fluid is very useful in understanding several physical problems because it possesses the mechanism to illustrate rheological complex fluids such as blood, lubricants containing small amount of high polymer additive, liquid crystals, human blood, synovial joint, electro-rheological fluids and synthetic fluids. In this view the model formulated by Stokes [15] and represents to predict micro structural characteristics (particle size) of physiological suspensions with good precision. Mekheimer [16] studied the problem of the peristaltic transport of a couple stress fluid in a uniform and non-uniform channel. The peristaltic flow of a couple stress fluid under the effect of induced magnetic field in an asymmetric channel have been observed by Nadeem and Akram [17], Effect of the induced magnetic field on peristaltic flow of a magneto-couple stress fluid was studied by Mekheimer [18]. His study indicates that the current density at the center of the channel is higher for a couple stress fluid than a Newtonian fluid, and it also decreases as the transverse magnetic field increases. Pandey and Chaube [19] have investigated the peristaltic transport of a couple stress fluid in a channel with compliant walls. They have determined that the mean velocity at boundaries decreases with increasing couple-stress parameter and wall damping and increases with increase of wall tension and wall elasticity.

It is valuable to mention that the intrauterine fluid flow in a sagittal cross - section of non-pregnant uterus caused by myometrial contractions is a peristaltic-type fluid motion. Further, myometrial contractions may discloses a narrow channel enclosed by two fairly parallel walls with wave trains having different amplitudes and phase difference [20]. The peristaltic motion of Williamson nanofluids in a tapered asymmetric channel under the Effects of thermal radiation parameter and magnetic field was analyzed by Kothandapani and Prakash [21]. Dhanapal et al. have presented a mathematical model to study wall induced flow of a micropolar nanofluid in the most generalized channel with the presence of heat source and thermal radiation parameters [22]. In view of the above mentioned reasons, a new mathematical/theoretical analysis of peristaltic motion of a couple stress fluid in the most generalized form of the channel mentioned as the tapered asymmetric channel is investigated. To the best of our knowledge, no endeavor has been reported yet to discuss the peristaltic flow of a couple stress fluid through in the tapered asymmetric channel under the assumptions of long wavelength and low Reynolds number. The exact solutions of pressure gradient, axial velocity and stream function are obtained. The influence of various pertinent parameters on the flow characteristics are discussed in details with the help of graphs.

2. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Let us consider a peristaltic flow of a Couple stress fluids through two-dimensional channel of non-uniform thickness $2d$ with a sinusoidal wave traveling with constant speed c , asymmetric with respect to its axis (see Fig. 1). Let $\bar{y} = H_1$ and $\bar{y} = H_2$ be respectively the upper and lower wall boundaries of the tapered asymmetric channel. The resulting tapered asymmetric channel walls are defined as

$$H_1(\bar{x}, \bar{t}) = d + m'\bar{x} + a_2 \sin\left[\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}(\bar{x} - c\bar{t})\right], \quad \dots \text{upper wall} \quad (1)$$

$$H_2(\bar{x}, \bar{t}) = -d - m'\bar{x} - a_1 \sin\left[\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}(\bar{x} - c\bar{t}) + \phi\right]. \quad \dots \text{lower wall} \quad (2)$$

where a_1 and a_2 are the amplitudes of wave lower and upper walls respectively, λ is the wavelength, c is the phase speed of the wave, m' ($m' \ll 1$) is the non-uniform parameter, the phase difference ϕ varies in the range $0 \leq \phi \leq \pi$, $\phi = 0$ corresponds to symmetric channel with waves out of the phase i.e. both walls move towards the outward or inward simultaneously and further a_1 , a_2 , d and ϕ satisfy the condition for the divergence channel at the inlet of flow, otherwise both the walls gets collided.

$$a_1^2 + a_2^2 + 2a_1a_2 \cos\phi \leq (2d)^2. \quad (3)$$

For a couple stress fluid, the constitutive equations are

$$T_{ji,j} + \rho f_i = \rho \frac{dv_i}{dt}, \quad (4)$$

$$e_{ijk}T_{jk}^A + M_{ji,j} + \rho C_i = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$\tau_{ij} = -\bar{p}\delta_{ij} + 2\mu d_{ij}, \quad (6)$$

$$\mu_{ij} = 4\eta\varpi_{ji} + \eta'\varpi_{i,j}, \quad (7)$$

In the above equations C_i is the body moment per unit mass, f_i is the body force vector per unit mass, τ_{jk} and T_{jk}^A are the symmetric and anti symmetric parts of the stress tensor T , respectively, M_{ij} is the couple-stress tensor, μ_{ij} is the deviatoric part of M_{ij} , ϖ_i is the vorticity vector, d_{ij} is the symmetric part of the velocity gradient, μ is the viscosity of the fluid, $\bar{p}$ is the pressure, δ_{ij} is the Kroneker delta, ρ is the density and η and η' are constant associated with the couple stress.

The equations of continuity and momentum are given as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{x}} + \frac{\partial \bar{v}}{\partial \bar{y}} = 0, \quad (8)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{t}} + \bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{x}} + \bar{v} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{y}} \right) = -\frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial \bar{x}} + \mu \nabla^2 \bar{u} - \eta \nabla^4 \bar{u}, \quad (9)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \bar{v}}{\partial t} + \bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{v}}{\partial \bar{x}} + \bar{v} \frac{\partial \bar{v}}{\partial \bar{y}} \right) = -\frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial \bar{y}} + \mu \nabla^2 \bar{v} - \eta \nabla^4 \bar{v}, \quad (10)$$

where

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \bar{x}^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \bar{y}^2}, \quad \nabla^4 = \nabla^2 \nabla^2$$

Defining the following non-dimensional parameters are introduced in Eqs. (8)-(10),

$$x = \frac{\bar{x}}{\lambda}, y = \frac{\bar{y}}{d_1}, t = \frac{c\bar{t}}{\lambda}, u = \frac{\bar{u}}{c}, v = \frac{\bar{v}}{c\delta}, \delta = \frac{d}{\lambda}, h_1 = \frac{H_1}{d}, h_2 = \frac{H_2}{d}, p = \frac{d^2 \bar{p}}{c\lambda\mu},$$

$$Re = \frac{cd\rho}{\mu}, m = \frac{m'\lambda}{d}, a = \frac{a_1}{d}, b = \frac{a_2}{d}, \gamma^2 = \frac{c\mu^2}{\eta}. \quad (11)$$

in which δ and Re represent the wave number and Reynolds number respectively, whereas a and b are non-dimensional amplitudes of the lower and upper walls respectively and m is non-uniform parameter,

$$Re \delta \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \left(\delta^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) - \frac{1}{\gamma^2} \left(\delta^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \right) \left(\delta^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right), \quad (12)$$

$$Re \delta^3 \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \delta^2 \left(\delta^2 \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} \right) - \frac{\delta^2}{\gamma^2} \left(\delta^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \right) \left(\delta^2 \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} \right), \quad (13)$$

in which the equation of continuity will be identically satisfied.

Under the assumptions of long wavelength $\delta \ll 1$ and low Reynolds number, neglecting the terms δ and its higher orders in Eqs. (12)-(13), one can obtain,

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \frac{1}{\gamma^2} \frac{\partial^4 u}{\partial y^4}, \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (15)$$

$$u = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = h_1 = 1 + mx + b \sin(2\pi(x-t)), \quad (16)$$

$$u = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = h_2 = -1 - mx - a \sin(2\pi(x-t) + \phi) \quad (17)$$

3. RATE OF VOLUME FLOW

If we introduce the wave frame having the coordinates (x, y) which travel in the X – direction with the same wave velocity (c) , then the unsteady flow in the laboratory frame $(\bar{x}, \bar{y})$ can be treated as steady. The coordinates and velocities in the two frames are related by

$$x = \bar{x} - ct, y = \bar{y}, u = \bar{u} - c, v = \bar{v} \quad (18)$$

where u, v are the velocity components in the wave frame (x, y) .

The instantaneous volume flow rate $\bar{Q}(\bar{x}, \bar{t})$ in the stationary frame is given by

$$\bar{Q}(\bar{x}, \bar{t}) = \int_{H_2(\bar{x}, \bar{t})}^{H_1(\bar{x}, \bar{t})} u(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{t}) d\bar{y} \quad (19)$$

in which H_1 and H_2 are the function of $\bar{x}$ and $\bar{t}$.

Substituting Eq.(18) into Eq.(19), we obtain,

$$\bar{Q}(\bar{x}, \bar{t}) = \bar{q} + cH_1 - cH_2$$

$$\text{where } \bar{q} = \int_{H_2}^{H_1} u(x, y) dy, \quad (20)$$

is the rate of volume flow in the moving frame.

The time-averaged flow over a period $(T = \lambda/c)$ at a fixed position X is defined as

$$\bar{Q} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T Q dt. \quad (21)$$

If we substitute Eq.(20) into Eq.(21) and integrating, we get [23, 31-33]

$$\bar{Q} = \bar{q} + a_1 c \sin \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (X - ct) + a_2 c \sin \left[\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (X - ct) + \phi \right]. \quad (22)$$

If we find the dimensionless mean flows F , in the laboratory frame, and Θ , in the wave frame, according to

$$F = \frac{\bar{Q}}{cd}, \quad \Theta = \frac{\bar{q}}{cd}, \quad (23)$$

one finds that Eq. (22) becomes, after using Eqs.(23 & 11)

$$F(x, t) = \Theta + a \sin 2\pi(x - t) + b \sin [2\pi(x - t) + \phi] \quad (24)$$

in which

$$F = \int_{h_2}^{h_1} u dy. \quad (25)$$

4. EXACT SOLUTION

The exact solution of the problem of Eqs. (14-17) is

$$u = \frac{1}{(\partial p / \partial x)} \left[A_4 + A_3 y + A_2 \cosh(\gamma y) + A_1 \sinh(\gamma y) + \frac{y^2}{2} \right], \quad (26)$$

The corresponding stream function is

$$\psi = \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \left(A_4 y + \frac{A_3 y^2}{2} + \frac{A_2 \sinh(\gamma y)}{\gamma} + A_1 \left(\frac{\cosh(\gamma y) - 1}{\gamma} \right) + \frac{y^3}{6} \right), \quad (27)$$

where the constant of integration is taken to be zero. Through Eq.(25) we find that

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = \frac{6\gamma F}{\left(6\gamma A_4 (h_1 - h_2) + 3\gamma A_3 (h_1^2 - h_2^2) + 6A_2 (\sinh(\gamma h_1) - \sinh(\gamma h_2)) \right. \\ \left. + 6A_1 (\cosh(\gamma h_1) - \cosh(\gamma h_2)) + \gamma (h_1^3 - h_2^3) \right)}, \quad (28)$$

where

$$A_1 = \frac{(\cosh(\gamma h_1) - \cosh(\gamma h_2))}{\gamma^2 \sinh(\gamma (h_1 - h_2))},$$

$$A_2 = -\frac{(\gamma^2 A_1 \sinh(\gamma h_1) + 1)}{\gamma^2 \cosh(\gamma h_1)},$$

$$A_3 = \frac{2A_2 (\cosh(\gamma h_2) - \cosh(\gamma h_1)) + 2A_1 (\sinh(\gamma h_2) - \sinh(\gamma h_1)) + (h_2^2 - h_1^2)}{2(h_1 - h_2)},$$

$$A_4 = -(A_3 h_1 + A_2 \cosh(\gamma h_1) + A_1 \sinh(\gamma h_1) + (h_1^2 / 2)),$$

The non-dimensional expression for the pressure rise $\Delta p_\lambda(t)$ is given as follows:

$$\Delta p_\lambda(t) = \int_0^1 \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} dx, \quad (29)$$

5. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section demonstrates the effects of various values of the rheological parameter (γ), geometrical parameters like amplitudes of upper and lower walls (a & b), phase difference (ϕ) and non-uniform parameter (k) and the time average mean-flow rate ($\bar{Q}$) on the axial velocity, the average rise in pressure per wavelength and trapping. Fig.2(a) illustrates the change of the axial velocity of the fluid versus the width of the tapered asymmetric channel for the different values of the couple stress parameter (γ). One can observe from the figure that the axial velocity decreases as the couple stress parameter increases. Physiologically, it may be illuminated that the flow of infected urine in ureter due to suspended particles (e.g., urine from a diseased kidney) is hindered. Further, in wider part of the channel $y \in [-2.2, -1.2]$ and $y \in [0.6, 1.8]$, the variation in velocity relatively small. Fig.2 (b) is made to see the influence of the time average mean-flow rate ($\bar{Q}$). It shows that the velocity of the fluid is parabolic in nature. In addition to that, an increase in increase in the time average mean flow rate ($\bar{Q}$) leads to decrease in the horizontal velocity (u). The impact of the phase difference (ϕ) on the velocity is represented in Fig.2(c) with the fixed values of other parameters. It is observed that the axial velocity of the fluid, in the central

part of the channel, decreases with increasing ϕ . The effects of amplitude of upper wall on the velocity is displayed in Fig.2(d). This graph reveals that an increase in (a) results in an increase in the velocity of the fluid.

Fig. 3 is exposed to see the influence various values of the amplitude of upper wall (b) , non-uniform parameter (k) , phase difference (ϕ) and the couple stress parameter (γ) on average rise in pressure (ΔP) versus the time average mean-flow rate $(\bar{Q})$ with the fixed values other parameters involved in the expression of ΔP . The graph can be sectored in four parts (i.e.) the upper right-hand quadrant (I) denotes the region of the peristaltic pumping wherein $\bar{Q} > 0$ and $\Delta P > 0$. Quadrant (II) is designated as augmented flow when $\bar{Q} > 0$ and $\Delta P < 0$. Quadrant (IV) in which $\bar{Q} < 0$ and $\Delta P > 0$ is called retrograde or backward pumping. It evidently indicates that the relation between ΔP and $\bar{Q}$ is a linear and both of them have inverse reciprocal relation. It is observed from Fig. 3a that with an increase in amplitude of upper wall b , the average rise in pressure decreases in peristaltic pumping. Moreover, free pumping ($\Delta P = 0$) is also become wider. Fig. 3b reveals that the relation between ΔP and $\bar{Q}$ for different values of non-uniform parameter (k) . One can find that for given ΔP , the flux $\bar{Q}$ depends on k and it decreases with increase of non-uniform parameter (k) . We notice from Fig. 3c that the pumping rate in peristaltic as well as in retrograde decreases when phase difference (ϕ) is increased. Fig. 3d gives the influences of couple-stress γ on ΔP . It is examined that an increase in γ results decrease in the peristaltic pumping rate, free pumping and adverse pressure gradient.

One of interesting phenomenon in peristaltic flow is trapping. The formation of an internally circulating bolus of the fluid by closed streamlines is called trapping and this trapped bolus pushed ahead along the peristaltic wave. The effects of couple-stress fluid parameter (γ) , mean flux $(\bar{Q})$ and non-uniform parameter (k) on the trapping are illustrated in Fig. 4. The remarkable notice on trapping phenomenon is that the appearing of bolus is present when fluid flow is induced by contraction/expansion of the tapered asymmetric channel. Moreover, it is also observed that the volume of the trapped bolus increases with increase of all the flow parameters k , $\bar{Q}$ and γ .

6. CONCLUSION

The problem of peristaltic flow of a couple stress fluid in the tapered asymmetric channel is discussed. A long-wavelength and low-Reynolds number approximations have been adopted. The exact expressions for horizontal velocity, horizontal pressure gradient and stream function are obtained analytically. Graphical results are obtainable for the pressure rise per wavelength friction forces on the upper and lower walls, horizontal pressure gradient and trapping. The main findings of the present analysis are listed below:

- In the entire figures, the large values of γ correspond to that of a Newtonian fluid.
- The magnitude of the velocity of Newtonian fluid is higher than couple-stress fluid.

- The rate of peristaltic pumping gets decreased with increasing non-uniform parameter and rheological parameter.
- The size of bolus increases with an increase of non-uniform parameter. Fig. 5 shows that our results are in agreement with Srivastava and Srivastava [23] when the amplitudes of both walls are equal and absence of the phase difference.

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Fig. 1. Schematic depiction of fluid flow induced by a tapered asymmetric channel

Fig. 2. The axial velocity distributions

(a): $a = 0.6, b = 0.5, \bar{Q} = 1.8, \phi = \pi/4, x = 0.2, t = 0.1$

(b): $a = 0.3, b = 0.7, \gamma = 1.5, \phi = \pi/4, x = 0.4, t = 0.2$ (c): $a = 0.5, b = 0.5, \bar{Q} = 1.7, \gamma = 1.5,$

$x = 0.1, t = 0$ (d): $b = 0.7, \bar{Q} = 1.9, \gamma = 1.5, \phi = \pi/4, x = 0.3, t = 0.2$

Fig. 3. Graph of average rise in pressure rise versus time-averaged flow rate

(a): $a = 0.4, k = 0.1, \phi = \pi/6, \gamma = 1.5$, (b): $a = 0.5, b = 0.7, \phi = \pi/4, \gamma = 5$ (c): $a = 0.6, b = 0.4, k = 0.2, \gamma = 1$, (d): $a = 0.4, b = 0.5, k = 0.1, \phi = \pi/6$

Fig. 5. Comparison results of variation of pressure rise over a wavelength of non-uniform tapered asymmetric channel.